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Measuring ELIXIR-IT impact

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ELIXIR IMPACT FOCUS GROUP AND ELIXIR-IT

This group aims to empower ELIXIR partners in evaluating and communicating their performance and impact, in support of the long-term sustainability of national Nodes.

- [Empowering ELIXIR Nodes to measure and communicate their performance and impact \(Staff Exchange\)](#)
- [Impact evaluation at Node-level - getting it done](#), co-funded by [ELIXIR-CONVERGE](#), which produced [ELIXIR's Impact Toolkit!](#) (Commissioned Services)

6. Impact case studies

<i>Assessing the scientific impact of ELIXIR Italy: an analysis of acknowledgements and citations from publications by ELIXIR Italy</i>	ELIXIR Italy	Slides (2023), and video recording (second half) [link] . ELIXIR Italy created its own Impact Dashboard [link] . The impact case study was carried out in conjunction with a field project [link] as part of the Rltrain Executive Master for Research Infrastructures [link]
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SPECIAL ISSUE | Open Access |

Demonstrating public value to funders and other stakeholders — the journey of ELIXIR, a virtual and distributed research infrastructure for life science data

Corinne S. Martin , Susanna Repo, Juan Arenas Márquez, Niklas Blomberg, Katharina B. Lauer, Xènia Pérez Sitjà, Premysl Velek, Ana M. P. Melo, Christine Stansberg ... [See all authors](#)

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EXECUTIVE MASTERS IN MANAGEMENT OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Develop your skills for leading Research Infrastructures with global impact

Impact: What, Why and How

- Stakeholders and beneficiaries in Research Infrastructures

Impact: What, Why and How

Main categories of direct impact for work funded by and through ELIXIR

Martin et al. (2021) Demonstrating public value to funders and other stakeholders — the journey of ELIXIR, a virtual and distributed research infrastructure for life science data. *Ann Public Coop Econ*, 00, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apce.12328>

Research efficiency: we make infrastructure, bioinformatics resources and processes faster, easier to use, and more integrated

Scientific legacy: we create and disseminate new knowledge on research infrastructure, bioinformatics resources and related guidelines

Benefits derived from working together: (i.e. relationship/social capital), we facilitate knowledge-sharing and cooperation

Public awareness: we raise awareness of socio-economic and societal benefits of bioinformatics and Open Science

Policy influence: we shape policy in the area of Open Science and FAIR

Equal opportunity: we raise awareness of diversity and inclusiveness

Bioinformatics resource uptake: we work to increase resource usage and appreciation by users

Research infrastructure sustainability: we work to increase ELIXIR's visibility with, and appreciation by, its funders

Skills development: (i.e. human capital), we upskill resource users and service providers

Suggested indicators — useful classification that covers all aspects of running a core facility

Objective	KPIs
Enabling scientific excellence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of user requests for access 2. Number of users served 3. Number of publications 4. Percentage of top (10%) cited publications
Delivery of education and training	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Number of master and PhD students using the RI 6. Training of people who are not RI staff
Enhancing collaboration in Europe	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Number of members of the RI from ESFRI countries 8. Share of users and publications per ESFRI member country
Facilitating economic activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Share of users associated with industry and publications with industry 10. Income from commercial activities and the number of entities paying for service
Outreach to the public	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. Engagement achieved by direct contact 12. Outreach through media 13. Outreach via the RI's own web and social media
Optimising data use	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 14. Number of publicly available data sets used externally
Provision of scientific advice	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 15. Participation by RIs in policy related activities 16. Citations in policy related publications
Facilitating international co-operation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 17. Share of users and publications per non-ESFRI member country 18. International trainees 19. Number of members of the RI from non-ESFRI countries
Optimising management	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 20. Revenues 21. Extent of resources made available

Mapped against ESFRI* 's *Objectives of greatest relevance for research infrastructures*

* European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures

Measuring ELIXIR-IT's scientific legacy via text-mining

*Martin et al. (2021)²⁵ published an initial list of indicators (and other evidence) for monitoring the performance and impact of ELIXIR. An updated version [\[link\]](#)

Impact area and stakeholders:

Legend:

RED: Indicators to be determined

Scope? Identifying the link with/to ELIXIR-IT

Objective: Enable regular and automatic retrieval of Europe PMC articles that are ELIXIR-IT related

- ☞ list of **publications** that have received funding and/or support from ELIXIR-IT:
- that may not have happened without ELIXIR-IT's funding and/or support
 - where a contribution from ELIXIR-IT can be identified
 - presenting developments related to the research infrastructure and its resources
... and their **citations!!**

How to acknowledge ELIXIR-IT funding and support

<https://elixir-italy.org/impact/#acknowledgment>

- If your work has received financial support (e.g. grant funding, event sponsorship) or other support (e.g. in-kind contribution, use of the infrastructure and its many services) linked to ELIXIR-IT (also known as ELIXIR-IIB and ELIXIR Italy) you need to visibly acknowledge ELIXIR-IT's contribution so it can be tracked and reported. We indeed maintain this website page of such ELIXIR-IT-supported publications.
- In written work, you may use the following statements:

This work was funded [or supported] by ELIXIR-IT (ELIXIR-IIB, ELIXIR-ITA, Elixir Italy, ELIXIR IIB, ELIXIR IT), the Italian research infrastructure for life-science data.

This project has received funding from... [adapt depending on the grant in consultation with the project manager and official guidance from the European Commission]

Measuring ELIXIR-IT Scientific Impact

ENABLING SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE

- **Number of Scientific publications** (66 in 2021 vs 88 in 2022) and citations (654 in 2021 and 871 in 2022) starting from 2015.

PROVISION OF SCIENTIFIC ADVICE

- **Citations in policy related publications.** No citations searching on *Overton database*. Overton is the world's largest searchable index of policy documents, guidelines, think tank publications and working papers.

- On-going, searching patent applications mentioning ELIXIR-IT resource names. Project Proposal on patent analysis in collaboration with the Hub

Visualisation in [ELIXIR-IT website](#)

ELIXIR-related Paper Mining in EPMC

Status	Search Methods/Tokens	EuroPMC ID (pmid)
Fine/Probably Fine	text_search_general:"ELIXIR-EXCELERATE"	28874117
Fine/Probably Fine	text_search_general:	
False Positive	ACK_FUND:201535	
False Positive	GRANT_ID:201535	
Fine/Probably Fine	text_search_country:	
False Positive	text_search_general:	
False Positive	text_search_subjectiv	

Impact

Publications

ELIXIR-IT members collaborate to publish research articles (peer-reviewed) on the development and operation of bioinformatics resources encompassing databases, tools, cloud computing, standards and training. These publications highlight ELIXIR-IT's scientific legacy as a research infrastructure, and their citations by others (in the open literature) demonstrate the extent of ELIXIR's contribution and appreciation by others.

Number of publications per year:

Citation counts per year:

Number of publications by ELIXIR-IT member (2015-2023):

Word cloud from publication keywords:

SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE- Measuring ELIXIR-IT's service impact via text-mining

Impact area and stakeholders:

*Martin et al. (2021)²⁵ published an initial list of indicators (and other evidence) for monitoring the performance and impact of ELIXIR. An updated version [\[link\]](#)

Legend:

RED: Indicators to be determined

Measuring ELIXIR-IT's service impact via text-mining

Publications citing ELIXIR-IT services

> 70 ELIXIR-IT Services in Bio.Tools (excluding Training and OMICS)

Number of services in the ELIXIR-IT SDP for the Data, Tools, Compute and Interoperability ELIXIR platforms. For each platform are reported both the number in the previous iteration of the SDP and the current one.

14,844 total citations

User Strategy & Access Policy

ENABLING SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE

- Number of user requests for access. ELIXIR resources are open sources and with free access. Control access by the ELIXIR AAI is increasing. Improvements in monitoring the ELIXIR-IT resources are under evaluation.
- Number of publications based on the research performed using facilities/resources of the RI.

ENHANCING COLLABORATION IN EUROPE

- Support and facilitate participation to Communities and Focus Group. An updated list including new lead and participants coming from ELIXIR-IT members engagement is available.

OPTIMISING MANAGEMENT

- List of grants awarded in the name of ELIXIR-IT or in which ELIXIR-IT members are funded partner <https://elixir-italy.org/projects/>

Measuring Socio-economic Impact.

FACILITATING ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES

Partnerships with industry. Income from commercial activities and the number of entities paying for service

NEW

Industry Engagement in collaboration with Italbiotec

First outcome: https://elixir-italy.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/ELIXIR-IT_ENG.pdf

What we are doing with industry and SMEs

■ ELIXIR member active in industry; ■ ELIXIR member; ■ Non-ELIXIR member.

Text version

EMBL-EBI (European Molecular Biology Laboratory - European Bioinformatics Institute)
EMBL-EBI Industry Partnerships. Disseminating cutting-edge technologies to industry. EMBL-EBI stores, shares and analyses data produced by life scientists all over the world. Work with us to solve your data challenges.

ELIXIR Italy

- **ELIXIR Innovation and SME Forum:** Data management in the life sciences - a driver for innovation in November 2019
- **Participation in the Staff Exchange Scheme** “Empowering ELIXIR Nodes to measure and communicate their performance and impact”
- **Dedicated Training Offer.** The Training Platform activated a collaboration with **Chiesi Farmaceutici S.p.A.**, Parma, to carry out customized training activities on Pharmaceutical Bioinformatics and main applications
- **Software tools licence Agreement.** The BioComputingUP lab of the University of Padova, member of the ELIXIR IT Node, renewed its commercial licence agreement with the global biopharmaceutical company Sanofi, for a new version of the software package **RING (Residue Interaction Network Generator)** belonging to the Service List of ELIXIR-IT .
- **Establishment of Research Contracts** signed with Italfarmaco SpA, Polismail srl, Fondazione Santa Lucia, Vetoquinol srl, Ulisse Biomed, for services provided by the omics platform.

OUTREACH TO THE PUBLIC **Objective: Enhancing understanding of what ELIXIR-IT do**

Branding Strategy ELIXIR-IT communication plan includes branding, visibility, stakeholders targeting and a variety of channels.

Following the principle that “the whole is greater than the sum of its parts”,

ELIXIR-IT has the ambition to raise an Italian Infrastructure for Bioinformatics distributed across multiple centers, **aims to bring together all the Italian researchers** working in the field of bioinformatics, **encouraging** the exchange and development of skills, **integrating** the various Italian bioinformatics resources that share international scientific recognition and are publicly available, and **to contribute** to their integration within the European infrastructure.

Communication Tools

TOOL	STAKEHOLDERS	IMPACT AREA
Website https://elixir-italy.org	Scientists, Policy Makers, Industry, General Public, Internal Staff	Scientific, Human Resources, Economy, Society, Policy
Social Media, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn	Scientists, all the national members and other Nodes	Scientific, Society
Brochure, Leaflets, Newsletter	Scientists, Policy Makers, Industry, General Public, Internal Staff	Scientific, Human Resources, Economy, Society, Policy
Publications	Scientists, Funders, Internal Staff	Scientific, Policy, Society
Mailing lists (Mailing List generale, LTEC, Platform,...)	Scientists, Funders, Internal Staff, Industry	Scientific, Society, Policy

OUTREACH TO THE PUBLIC. Bioinformatics resource uptake; Scientific legacy; Public awareness

ELIXIR-IT Website: 2022 vs 2023

Website Views	9.260	Compared to 7.206	+ 28,5%
Users	2.653	Compared to 2.219	+ 19,56%
Views per User	3,49	Compared to 3,25	+7,48%
Average Engagement Duration	1 m 06 s	Compared to 58,45 s	+13,57%

In the 2022/2023 period, there was a substantial **28.5%** increase in **website views**, totaling 9,260 compared to the previous 7,206 (2021/2022). The **number of users** also grew by **19.56%**, from 2,219 to 2,653. Additionally, **views per user** increased by 7.48%, and the **average engagement duration** on the site pages rose by 13.57%.

👉 **Indicators:** Numbers of visitors (page views) to the ELIXIR-IT website; time spent on each page

👉 **Indicators:** Number of followers/subscribers on social media (Twitter/X, LinkedIn, YouTube)

ELIXIR-IT Social

LinkedIn

Analytics

Last 30 day activity

26 ▲ 136.4%

Search appearances

Last 7 days

10 ▲ 400%

Unique visitors

20 ▲ 1,900%

New followers

303

Post impressions

[Start a post](#)

X (Twitter)

28 day summary with change over previous period

Tweet Impressions
325 ▲ 49.8%

Followers
663 ▲ 9

In the last **30 days**, the ELIXIR-IT **LinkedIn** Profile **was listed 26 times in the search results**. **20 new followers were gained by the LinkedIn profile**. **Post impressions** amount to about **300**.

As for **X (Twitter)**, a **49.8% increase** in impressions was observed over the last 30 days, accompanied by the acquisition of **9 new followers**.

This work has been developed with the contribution of all the impact ‘pioneers’ and other in ELIXIR’s extended family

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All-round support!

Elaine Westwick
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Comms. officer
Communications

Despoina Sousoni
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Innovation & industry

THANK YOU!

